

EUYD11 EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen, Denmark. Working Group Topics

**Danish
Presidency**
Council of the
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MINISTRY OF CHILDREN
AND EDUCATION

THE DANISH
YOUTH
COUNCIL

21-23 September 2025

**Danish
Presidency**
Council of the
European Union

Title: EUYD11 EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen, Denmark. Working Group Topics

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Published in September 2025

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17431275

Please quote as follows:

Bárta O., Moxon D. (2025). EUYD11 EU Youth Conference in Copenhagen, Denmark. Working Group Topics. 10.5281/zenodo.17431275

Introduction

8 working groups took place during the EU Youth Conference Copenhagen held in September 2025. The working group participants were supported in their deliberations by background papers listed below. These background papers provided an overview of the topic, results of the 11th cycle of the EU Youth Dialogue consultations related to the topics, overview of key information from other sources, and references for further reading.

Working Group 1: Erasmus+ 2028-2034 and Youth Organisations

What is this topic about?

One of the areas of focus of the current Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps (ESC) is supporting youth organisations. This is done, among other things, by building their capacities, and providing organisational support and cooperation opportunities with other youth organisations, particularly with those that target young people with fewer opportunities¹.

In concrete terms, the Erasmus+ offers opportunities for youth workers to undergo trainings and mobilities, for youth organisations to get accredited and therefore have access to simplified funding options², and they can create projects in which they focus on cooperation with other organisations (Key Action 2)³.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should support youth organisations.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”⁴. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

What did young people say in the consultations?

The topic of youth organisations was not widely commented upon within replies to the consultation question on the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027 - but it was clear that youth organisations were understood to be one of many key stakeholders in the programme. Some respondents emphasised the need for **continuity of support and funding** for youth organisations to enhance the EU youth programmes overall.

“We can better use Erasmus+ by increasing the amount of money available to youth organisations, increas[ing] the number of staff to support organisations in national agencies

¹ [Capacity building in the field of youth - Erasmus+](#)

² [Mobility opportunities for accredited Erasmus organisations in the field of youth](#)

³ [Opportunities for organisations](#)

⁴ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

making applications and ensure a wider and more diverse group of young people get to participate” Young person responding to the Irish National Working Group

Others called for dedicated funding for specific types of youth organisations, such as those supporting LGBTQI+ youth.

The challenges that **smaller grassroots youth organisations** have in accessing EU youth programme grants were emphasised by other respondents. This was said to be caused by the administrative complexity of the programmes (see topic: Administrative and technical barriers). At the same time, some National Working Groups emphasised how young people who were involved with youth organisations were more able to access the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027, and were concerned with the programmes reaching beyond these groups.

National Youth Councils (NYCs) outside of the EU and International Non-Governmental Youth Organisations (INGYOs) emphasised the critical role that the youth programme played in terms of **protecting the shrinking space for youth civil society** and supporting rights-based organisations. Linked to this concern, there were calls for the prioritisation of rights-based and youth organisations, especially those working with marginalised groups or in politically sensitive areas. The role that the programmes could play in supporting these organisations was stressed by several NYCs and IYNGOs (see topic: Addressing New Challenges).

A small number of consultations replies also called for the **strengthening of training and mobility opportunities for youth workers** provided through the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027.

What else is good to know?

Evaluation of the Erasmus+ programme shows some positive developments, such as creation of new practices and methods, establishment of organisational networks, boost of innovation capacity, creation of new partnerships, incorporating green practices into projects, improved teaching practices, increased opportunities for cooperation (including preparations for the EU accession in some countries, and including across sectors), promotion of the EU values, capacity building, organisational development, and internationalisation.

According to the same evaluation, the Erasmus+ can do more to improve the following: often limited use of the project outputs and outcomes beyond direct participants and beneficiaries, limited longitudinal data on long-term effects of the projects on organisations and beyond, the persistence of a significant administrative burden for organisations, the difficulty in sustaining effects beyond the directly involved individuals and institutions, limited engagement of smaller organisations due to lack of administrative capacity and limited recourse to manage complex project requirements.

Evaluation of the European Solidarity Corps shows the programme contributed to strengthening of social cohesion, promotion of intercultural understanding, and addressing of local challenges, especially in rural areas and regions with declining local volunteering.

According to the same evaluation, the European Solidarity Corps can do more to improve the following: strengthen capacity building (especially connected to challenges of working with volunteers with fewer opportunities), support smaller organisations (those with project-based budgets struggled due to limited resources, leading to staff exhaustion and decreased administrative performance), and deal with the lack of follow-up funding (which also caused staff

turnover in participating organisations, which in turn limited knowledge transfer and threatened sustainability).

Do you want to read more?

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 Erasmus+ programme and the final evaluation of the 2014-2020 Erasmus+ programme. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0395&qid=1752646664581>

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation of the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0144>

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Interim evaluation for the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps, final evaluation for the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation for the 2014-2020 EU Aid Volunteers Initiative. Final Report. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8bd5657-0b86-11f0-b1a3-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Working Group 2: Erasmus+ 2028-2034 and Formal Education

What is this topic about?

The current Erasmus+ programme supports mobility and cooperation opportunities in school education, vocational education and training (VET), higher education, and adult education. These opportunities ultimately equip young people and participants of all ages with qualifications and skills needed for their engagement in society, intercultural understanding and successful transition into and within the labour market.

In detail, the Erasmus+ allows learners and staff in the following areas to go abroad: schools in general⁵, vocational education and training (VET)⁶, higher education⁷, and adult education⁸. It allows accrediting organisations in these fields to better support the educational institutions⁹. It

⁵ [Mobility for pupils and staff in school education](#)

⁶ [Mobility for learners and staff in vocational education and training](#)

⁷ [Mobility projects for higher education students and staff](#)

⁸ [Mobility for learners and staff in adult education](#)

⁹ [Erasmus accreditation in the fields of vocational education and training, school education and adult education](#)

also supports cooperation and capacity building activities in these areas¹⁰, including specific initiatives in VET¹¹ and higher education¹² sectors.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should support mobility and cooperation opportunities across all levels of formal education.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”¹³. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps” (ESC). Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

What did young people say in the consultations?

Considering the role of formal education within the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027, three main themes emerged across the consultation replies:

- 1. Better utilising schools and formal education as a tool for outreach and promotion.** Schools and other parts of formal education were often described as mechanisms through which outreach and the sharing of information about EU youth programme opportunities could be enhanced (see topic: Awareness). It was said that there was a need to change the perception that Erasmus+ was primarily a university exchange for academically competent students. Concerns were also raised about schools limiting participation opportunities to academically able students.
- 2. Embedding the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027 as part of citizenship education in schools and formal education.** Linked to the above, it was identified that the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027 should be embedded into civic education within schools and formal education. This was part of wider calls within other parts of the consultation to address the topic of the EU directly within civic education and to demonstrate better the opportunities the EU provides to young people.
- 3. Improving recognition of participants' civic learning** - A range of consultation replies called for better recognition of non-formal learning outcomes and civic contributions made through Erasmus+ and ESC. This was said to allow for better integration of civic learning into formal education and the labour market. Several measures were proposed for this, such as improving the Youthpass or other micro-credential systems and integrating civic engagement activities and volunteering into the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS). Tools like the Youthpass and micro-credential systems should be

¹⁰ [Capacity building in the field of vocational education and training \(VET\)](#)

[Capacity building in Higher Education](#)

[Erasmus+ Teacher Academies](#)

¹¹ [Centres of Vocational Excellence](#)

¹² [Alliances for innovation](#)

¹³ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

expanded and better integrated into formal education and the labour market to validate non-formal learning outcomes.

A small number of consultation replies also highlighted the need for **better aligning Erasmus+ with the labour market** through more vocational and practice-based opportunities, such as internships, apprenticeships, and job-shadowing. It was said that young people in vocational paths often feel left out of international programmes, even though they are eager to gain skills and experience beyond their immediate environment.

What else is good to know?

The European University Association states that there are some positive developments in the formal education area, such as supporting innovation and capacity developments in schools, creating high-quality opportunities for mobility, supporting intra-European and international university collaboration as well as collaboration with non-university partners. Erasmus+ also supports inclusion and diversity, democracy and civic engagement, digital transformation, and environment and climate action, and these are all seen as highly relevant priorities for the higher education sector. The Erasmus Student Network points out that the Erasmus+ programme is seen by students as inclusive, as contributing to their skills development, and as contributing to their civic development.

Nevertheless, the European University Association also highlighted the need for further developments, such as simplification and improvement of managerial and digital instruments. The Erasmus Student Network noted that increases in grants are not enough to offset record high living costs, and that scams and lack of information are problematic (especially in the domain of student housing). Students also reported various other barriers: lack of funding (35% of students), challenges finding accommodation (35%) and problems with the courses and other academic aspects, such as recognition or changes in documentation (34%). Complex and lengthy application processes for international student mobility are reported as barriers by 56% of respondents.

Do you want to read more?

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Use and impact of the Erasmus+ programme (2021-27) at higher education institutions Survey report and recommendations. Online, available at https://www.eua.eu/images/publications/Publication_PDFs/Erasmus_MidTerm_Report.pdf

European Parliament Erasmus+ 2021-2027 Implementation Report. The Experience of Higher Education Students: Contribution of the Erasmus Student Network. Online, available at https://esn.org/sites/default/files/news/erasmus_parliament_implementation_report.pdf

Working Group 3: Erasmus+ 2028-2034 and Youth Volunteering and Solidarity

What is this topic about?

The current European Solidarity Corps programme¹⁴ (ESC) encourages young people to participate in projects, either abroad or in their own country, by providing funding and other forms of support. It offers an empowering experience for young people who wish to help, learn, and develop, while also serving as a single-entry point for solidarity activities, primarily volunteering, across the EU and beyond.

In detail, the European Solidarity Corps programme supports short and long-term volunteering¹⁵, Solidarity Projects¹⁶ focusing on bringing positive changes to local communities, and Humanitarian Aid Volunteering¹⁷ which enables young people to support third countries in case of a humanitarian emergency.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should support youth volunteering and solidarity in Europe.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”¹⁸. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

¹⁴ [European Solidarity Corps](#)

¹⁵ [Volunteering activities](#)

¹⁶ [Solidarity Projects](#)

¹⁷ [Humanitarian Aid Volunteering](#)

¹⁸ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

What did young people say in the consultations?

A common call within the qualitative consultation was to **strengthen the opportunities provided for local volunteering and solidarity**, and to increase the local community impact of projects funded through the programmes. The Romanian National Working Group highlighted the need to *'Support youth-led projects at the local level, so that young people can see the impact of the EU in their own communities'*.

The value of supporting young people to **engage at the local level**, through civic mini projects or youth-led campaigns or similar, **especially as a follow-on from an international mobility experience**, was widely highlighted. This was said to reinforce the idea that civic responsibility is ongoing and rooted both locally and transnationally.

Many participants felt motivated by their Erasmus+ or ESC experience but lacked direction after their project ended. It was said that local follow-on measures would help increase long-term civic engagement and maximise the impacts of the ESC and Erasmus+ 2021-2027. The desire was to enable young people to contribute meaningfully to their home communities either before departure or after returning.

'Some [young people] suggested creating alumni networks or local action hubs, where young people could continue their engagement with the themes they explored during their Erasmus+ or ESC projects, such as climate action or inclusion. This would ensure the impact of the programme continues long after the mobility period ends.' Maltese National Working Group Report

Various concrete suggestions for follow-on support were made, such as microgrants for participants presenting the outcomes of their work in schools and community spaces, and alumni networks and peer mentorships linked to volunteering themes. Emphasis was typically placed on enabling young people to contribute to addressing issues of concern in their local community, such as environmental clean-ups, supporting vulnerable people, combating discrimination, or initiatives on mental health.

60% to 71% of young people who took part in the consultation standardised survey totally or to a large extent agree that engagement in various mobility opportunities helps them be more active in their communities and in Europe. 60% of them believe that volunteering abroad helps them make a positive change.

What else is good to know?

The European Solidarity Corps programme evaluation shows that it is highly relevant to enhance social cohesion, individual development, and inclusion. Participants report significant personal growth as well as meaningfully contributing to the development of local communities. It is recommended that the programme in the future supports further development of young people beyond the project scope, in areas such as employment.

The report highlighted that the programme systematically positively impacts individuals, organisations, and communities, specifically: *"At the individual level, participants in the European Solidarity Corps programme receive significant personal, professional, and educational growth, as well as an increase in civic engagement and social awareness. (...) For organisations, the European Solidarity Corps has facilitated significant improvements in project*

management, diversity, and inclusion practices. (...) At the local and community level, the European Solidarity Corps strengthened social cohesion and intercultural understanding while addressing local challenges.” The programme also brings added value on the European level, with benefits such as strengthening of the European identity, fostering of European values such as democracy or human rights, or deepening the sense of belonging to the European community.

Funding proved to be one of the weak sides of the programme, as allocated budgets did not manage to keep pace with inflation, and were strained when it came to supporting young people with fewer opportunities. As a result, only a fraction of interested participants were allowed to enter the programme. The report suggested that budgets should be scaled up to enable the programme to reach more young people, and to continue to achieve the positive impacts it has proven to bring.

The report also highlights that in case the European Solidarity Corps would be integrated into the Erasmus+ programme, it might prove challenging to keep the unique focus of the European Solidarity Corps on volunteering and solidarity.

Do you want to read more?

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Working Group 4: Horizontal Priorities of Erasmus+ 2028-2034

What is this topic about?

The Erasmus+ programme has currently four horizontal priorities¹⁹. These are: (1) environment and fight against climate change, (2) digital transformation, (3) participation in democratic life, and (4) inclusion and diversity.

This working group will produce recommendations on what the priorities of the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should be.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”²⁰. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

What did young people say in the consultations?

Within the qualitative consultation, National Working Groups (NWGs) and National Youth Councils (NYCs) reports did not comment specifically on which horizontal priorities are desired for the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034. However, across the various areas of discussion, it is clear that emphasis is placed on two themes.

- **Civic engagement and political participation** - with emphasis on promoting young democratic participation, increasing civic engagement, and developing an understanding of the EU.
- **Inclusion and diversity** - with emphasis on using the programmes to both provide support for young people with fewer opportunities, as well as on reducing polarisation, challenging racism and discrimination.

Some mention was made of sustainability and digitisation, but these were not prominent themes within the consultation replies. This may be a reflection of the consultation question, which asked about active citizenship and did not specifically address these areas.

The EU Youth Dialogue standardised survey question on European Youth Goals²¹ is relevant to understanding the **general priorities of young people**. Though it may not be the case that all of these priorities are suitable for consideration as priorities *for the next Erasmus+ programme 2028-2034*.

In the survey, 73% of young people considered mental health and well-being to be totally or to a large extent important. Many other priorities are also rated high by over 70% of young people, such as sustainability, quality of learning and employment, or participation in policymaking.

¹⁹ [Priorities of the Erasmus+ Programme](#)

²⁰ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

²¹ [European Youth Goals](#)

What else is good to know?

Evaluation of the Erasmus+ programme shows that green transition has been increasingly often a topic of projects, and that green transport options are increasingly utilised within the funded projects. Nevertheless, insufficient travel reimbursement thresholds as well as lack of time and cost allocation for travelling were identified as key issues in this priority. Implementation of the digital transformation priority contributed to development of digital skills in participants, and also in willingness to use digital technologies more in their lives.

The priority “participation in democratic life” has been a long-term focus of funded projects, and participants “*have shown increased knowledge about democratic values and a willingness to engage more actively in democratic processes*”. The Erasmus+ is also seen as highly inclusive: “*Inclusion and diversity is considered the most successfully addressed and implemented horizontal priority, with progress being recorded in the various programme countries and across the programme’s sectors.*”

Do you want to read more?

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Working Group 5: Erasmus+ 2028-2034 and the Link to Citizenship Skills

What is this topic about?

The Erasmus+ programme can make a valuable contribution to young people's citizenship skills, including democratic skills and intercultural understanding. This is particularly relevant in times of growing anti-democratic tendencies.

“Participation in democratic life, common values and civic engagement” is one of the horizontal priorities of Erasmus+ programme²², and active citizenship is also at the core of the European Solidarity Corps programme²³.

This working group will develop recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should foster citizenship skills and related competences.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”²⁴. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” (ESC) programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

²² [Priorities of the Erasmus+ Programme](#)

²³ [European Solidarity Corps – Our Mission and Principles](#)

²⁴ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

What did young people say in the consultations?

60% to 71% of young people who took part in the EU Youth Dialogue standardised survey totally or to a large extent agree that engagement in various mobility opportunities helps them be more active in their communities and in Europe, showcasing a wide acknowledgement of young people on the positive benefits of mobility to active citizenship.

Multiple National Working Groups (NWGs) and National Youth Councils (NYCs) reports highlighted the way that **young people in the consultation saw the connection between the Erasmus+ and ESC and active citizenship as strong, but not always explicit**. Young people said the programmes naturally support active citizenship, by exposing participants to new perspectives, encouraging teamwork, and strengthening a sense of belonging to Europe, but that this could be made more intentional. Although the participants described the experience as transformative, particularly in terms of personal development, language learning, and gaining confidence, many did not initially connect these experiences with broader civic competencies. It was argued that whilst the personal dimension side of the programmes was well realised, the link to civic competences could still be more intentional as tools for nurturing democratic values, community involvement, and European solidarity.

‘Despite the positive experiences, young people point out that they often perceive Erasmus primarily as an academic or cultural experience, rather than as an EU project promoting active citizenship or political participation. For most, Erasmus remains a school project not directly linked to understanding the workings of the EU or encouraging their social engagement.’ Slovenian NWG Report

To link citizenship skills more explicitly to the programme, three general areas of improvement were highlighted across the reports.

- 1. Increasing the pedagogical support and training opportunities provided**, so that more projects contain strong formal and non-formal learning opportunities explicitly linked to citizenship. Specific suggestions for this included adding training components on civic education, democratic participation, youth rights, human rights, EU awareness, EU values, and interculturality. Specific training modules could be added to learning mobilities, perhaps even on a mandatory basis.

‘Erasmus+ and the European Solidarity Corps should integrate educational pathways on the EU, its values and democratic functioning and European citizenship rights: the inclusion of mandatory modules, even in non-formal form, on these topics would strengthen the awareness and civic engagement of participants.’ Italian NWG Report

- 2. Stronger follow-on activities after the end of each mobility** - giving participants the opportunities to volunteer and apply their civic skills in some form of local solidarity or volunteering projects. It was said that many young people return from mobility experiences with essential skills, but without the tools to act in their community. There was a need to help transition short-term participation into long-term civic engagement and leadership (See topic: Volunteering and Solidarity).

Using the programmes to **enhance intercultural dialogue and actively combat discrimination**. According to the Hungarian NWG, *‘Erasmus+ already builds friendships and reshapes views on*

Europe. To deepen this, programmes should further encourage dialogue around diversity, cultural exchange, and solidarity...to support the idea of an EU based on mutual understanding and cohesion.'

What else is good to know?

Evaluation of the European Solidarity Corps shows that the programme “*plays a critical role in addressing and mitigating the rising challenges of anti-EU and anti-democratic sentiments.*” As such, it is seen as crucial for active citizenship promotion, and safeguarding support for democracy. Moreover, the volunteers engaged in the European Solidarity Corps programme are linked to “*broader societal, political, and citizenship engagement*”. The evaluation showed that young people “*who engage in solidarity activities develop a keen interest in the social and political spheres, a natural progression from community service to active citizenship*”.

Erasmus+ evaluation showed many effects on participants of the programme. “*At the individual level, these include improved soft skills, such as intercultural competence, language proficiency and adaptability, increased European identity and active citizenship.*” DiscoverEU has proved to be also impactful in this area, according to the Erasmus+ evaluation: “*The evidence suggests that, as a direct result of this participation, youth experienced an increase in their sense of initiative and entrepreneurship, positive feelings towards the EU, active citizenship, likelihood of feeling fully responsible for being successful in education, training or job, and learning propensity.*” Moreover, RAY Network (Research-based analysis of European youth programmes) studies suggest similarly positive results²⁵.

Do you want to read more?

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 Erasmus+ programme and the final evaluation of the 2014-2020 Erasmus+ programme. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0395&qid=1752646664581>

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SUPPORT STUDY FOR THE ERASMUS+ 2021-2027 INTERIM EVALUATION AND THE ERASMUS+ 2014-2020 FINAL EVALUATION. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8c800c3f-6099-11f0-a9d0-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Interim evaluation for the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps, final evaluation for the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation for the 2014-2020 EU Aid Volunteers Initiative. Final Report. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8bd5657-0b86-11f0-b1a3-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

²⁵ [Long-term effects of Erasmus+ Youth in Action on participation and citizenship](#)

Working Group 6: Inclusion and Accessibility of Erasmus+ 2028-2034

What is this topic about?

Inclusion is a priority of the current EU Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and European Solidarity Corps (ESC) programmes²⁶, with a focus on addressing the barriers that different target groups may face in accessing programme opportunities. This includes people from diverse cultural, social, and economic backgrounds, as well as people with disabilities, migrants, and people living in remote or rural areas. The Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC programmes also have their own *Inclusion and Diversity Strategy 2021-2027*²⁷, which is supported by an implementation guide²⁸.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should strengthen inclusiveness and accessibility for diverse groups of young people.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”²⁹. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

What did young people say in the consultations?

According to the results of the EU Youth Dialogue standardised survey, in general, young people with fewer opportunities see mobility opportunities as more beneficial than their counterparts from the majority group. In addition, young people from financially comfortable backgrounds, women, and young people who are in education, employment, or training are more likely to see the mobility opportunities as beneficial to their active citizenship development (compared to their respective counterparts: young people who are less financially comfortable, men, and young people Not in Employment, Education or Training (NEETs).

Inclusion and accessibility were widely discussed topics amongst the consultation respondents. It was clear that enhancing the accessibility of the programmes was a priority for the large majority of National Working Groups (NWGs) and National Youth Councils (NYCs). There was concern that the current generation of Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC was not equally accessible and was perceived as intended for more privileged young people.

‘Many [young people] expressed concern that access remains unequal, with urban youth, university students, or those in better-funded schools disproportionately benefiting. Meanwhile, young people in rural areas, vocational schools, or outside of formal education often remain unaware of these opportunities or perceive them as “not for people like me.”’ Polish NWG

Report

²⁶ [Priorities of the Erasmus+ Programme](#)
[European Solidarity Corps: Principles](#)

²⁷ [Inclusion and Diversity Strategy 2021-2027](#)

²⁸ [Implementation guidelines - Erasmus+ and European Solidarity Corps Inclusion and Diversity Strategy](#)

²⁹ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

NWGs identified specific barriers to young people with fewer opportunities accessing the programmes, and these included:

- **Lack of information** about the programme and **lack of access to support** when applying (see topic: Awareness)
- **Complexity of language** within programme material and application forms
- **Financial barriers associated with the programmes.** The Erasmus Student Network highlighted that, according to their research, over one third of students experience significant difficulties securing affordable housing during Erasmus+ exchanges.

'Economically disadvantaged youth and those living outside major cities also voiced concerns about affordability - not necessarily of the programme itself, which is often funded, but of associated costs, such as preparation, travel, or missed income. A few young people said they work part-time or have family responsibilities that make participation in long-term mobility programmes difficult.' Estonian NWG report

Proposals to enhance accessibility and inclusion included:

- **Reducing the complexity** of application forms and **simplifying the language** used in program materials.
- **Increasing the levels of financial support** available through the programs to young people with fewer opportunities.
- **Creation of shorter-term or new formats** - with emphasis on project formats which require less time commitment or travelling to enable young people with work or family commitments to participate, and to create a 'first step' opportunity for those who were uncertain about participating.
- **Creation of accessibility standards** - to take into account the specific needs of supporting different groups of young people with fewer opportunities.

Targeted and tailored outreach support for young people with fewer opportunities was also widely emphasised. It was said to be important to reach beyond youth organisations and universities, and reach settings such as vocational schools, rural areas, and youth work settings. The role of **mentors or alumni** who could both provide support and act as inspiration was also highlighted.

What else is good to know?

The evaluation of Erasmus+ shows that the programme is seen as highly inclusive: *"Inclusion and diversity is considered the most successfully addressed and implemented horizontal priority, with progress being recorded in the various programme countries and across the programme's sectors."* The evaluation also highlighted that the dedicated Inclusion and Diversity Strategy assisted actors in various sectors (youth, schools, etc.) in implementing the Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC in a coherently inclusive manner.

Do you want to read more?

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 Erasmus+ programme and the final evaluation of the 2014-2020 Erasmus+ programme. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0395&qid=1752646664581>

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation of the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0144>

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SUPPORT STUDY FOR THE ERASMUS+ 2021-2027 INTERIM EVALUATION AND THE ERASMUS+ 2014-2020 FINAL EVALUATION. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/8c800c3f-6099-11f0-a9d0-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Interim evaluation for the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps, final evaluation for the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation for the 2014-2020 EU Aid Volunteers Initiative. Final Report. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8bd5657-0b86-11f0-b1a3-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Working Group 7: Erasmus+ 2028-2034 Addressing New Challenges

What is this topic about?

The European Union is facing increasingly complex crises and challenges. From growing geopolitical tensions and conflicts, hybrid and cybersecurity threats, and foreign information manipulation and interference, to climate change and increasing natural disasters. These challenges have required a higher degree of civic resilience and preparedness among young people to be able to navigate uncertain times.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should address the current needs of young people in the face of uncertain times.

Please note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”³⁰. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps” (ESC). Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both, as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

³⁰ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

What did young people say in the consultations?

Responses to the consultation question on Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC did not generally address this topic. It was primarily non-EU National Youth Councils (NYCs) and International Non-Governmental Youth Organisations (INGYOs) who discussed these areas.

The World Organisation of the Scout Movement raised concerns over environmental sustainability, climate justice and peace and security. They argued that for the EU to remain a robust humanitarian actor, it must ensure the stability of funding for youth organisations to address these topics through non-formal education.

Building on this, the Belarus NYC and the Turkish NYC highlighted the critical role the programs played in **supporting youth NGOs and human rights activists in countries with a shrinking civic space**, or where fundamental rights were under threat. They highlighted the potential that the programmes could play in providing direct funding to these organisations from the EU. They stressed the need for this funding to be delivered with either no national government interference or robust and transparent allocation mechanisms. This was felt to be essential to avoid the risk of Governments that were not supportive of rights-based youth NGOs diverting funding away from these organisations. Finally, the Ukrainian NYC highlighted the critical role the programs could play in conflict-affected areas as part of peace-building processes. To address some of these issues, it was argued that there was a need for non-EU organisations to have stronger access to the programmes.

Within the qualitative consultation, a number of topics were proposed across the various reports. Mirroring Eurobarometer³¹ results, two themes were prevalent.

- **Peacebuilding, security and protection from radicalisation** (or similar), where concerns were expressed about global threats relating to war and extremism, as well as strengthening democratic resilience in relation to this.
- **Economic security/cost of living and housing** (or similar).

There were also a number of calls to address concerns about **digitalisation**, incorporating topics such as media and information literacy, digital privacy, and the impact of AI. Concerns about disinformation and misinformation were raised as part of this, especially linked to the protection from radicalisation theme above.

What else is good to know?

The Erasmus+ evaluation summarises that the objectives of the current programme reflect well *“the most pressing socio-economic needs and challenges”*. Similarly, *“programme’s four horizontal priorities are also considered relevant to socio-economic needs and challenges”*. The European Solidarity Corps programme was evaluated similarly positively: *“The programme is highly relevant in addressing local societal needs due to its diverse formats and topics, enabling tailored projects. (...) The programme has also proved adaptable in responding to the impact of climate-related hazards (e.g. floods) and other disasters such as earthquakes. (...) The European*

³¹ [Youth and democracy](#)

Solidarity Corps addresses crucial needs of European society, especially in fostering participation in democratic life, inclusion, and diversity.”

Do you want to read more?

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 Erasmus+ programme and the final evaluation of the 2014-2020 Erasmus+ programme. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0395&qid=1752646664581>

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Interim evaluation for the 2021-2027 European Solidarity Corps, final evaluation for the 2018-2020 European Solidarity Corps and final evaluation for the 2014-2020 EU Aid Volunteers Initiative. Final Report. Online, available at <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c8bd5657-0b86-11f0-b1a3-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

Working Group 8: Young People’s Awareness of the Erasmus+ 2028-2034

What is this topic about?

Many young people view increased opportunities to study, work, volunteer, and travel abroad (e.g., Erasmus+, European Solidarity Corps, etc.) as benefits of the EU membership. However, despite the benefits and opportunities provided by the current Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and European Solidarity Corps (ESC) programmes, many young people are still not familiar with these. In this domain, the programmes have been supported by Eurodesk³², a pan-European network of youth information agencies which aim at delivering mobility related information to young people all around Europe.

This working group will produce recommendations on how the future Erasmus+ 2028-2034 should reach and engage more young people.

Please Note: The European Commission has recently presented the proposal “Erasmus+ Programme for the Period 2028–2034”³³. This proposal includes elements of the two existing programmes: “Erasmus+ 2021–2027” and the “European Solidarity Corps”. Since the Commission’s proposal merges the current “Erasmus+” and “European Solidarity Corps” programmes, participants are encouraged to draw on their knowledge and experiences of both,

³² [Eurodesk: Inspiring young people to fulfil their potential](#)

³³ [Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034](#)

as well as the findings of the consultation report, and use these as a basis for discussing the future programme: Erasmus+ 2028-2034.

What did young people say in the consultations?

Improving young people's awareness of the Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC was widely highlighted as an area for improvement within the consultation. There was a general view that the programmes are not well known enough amongst young people, and many perceive them as specifically for university students. There was also a concern that communication was unevenly distributed and did not effectively reach young people with fewer opportunities, and those outside of academic settings (see topic: Inclusion and Accessibility).

'Misconceptions remain, such as the belief that only university students can benefit from European mobility schemes, which leave out many groups, especially the younger ones or those who are not in higher education.' The French National Working Group Report

It was said that there is a need to **improve or reinvent the communication strategies** used for the Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC. Young people need to receive more accessible, transparent communication, in understandable language, with clear information about activities, costs and location, what to expect, how to prepare, and how participation can be of personal and professional benefit.

Suggestions from young people were highly consistent when it comes to the types of communication methods that could be used:

- The creation of an **all-in-one platform** or app that gathers all Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC programmes and opportunities in one place.
- Use of **social media** and communication channels that are already accessible, like Instagram, TikTok, YouTube.
- Promoting the Erasmus+ 2021-2027 more actively **in schools** (see topic: Formal Education)
- **Creative communications** such as photography or video contests, memes, and QR codes linking directly to applications.
- **Testimonials from past participants** - to help make the programmes feel more accessible, especially to those with no prior experience.
- **Targeted outreach** to groups who are usually not reached or familiar with the programmes - delivered through youth organisations and youth workers, as well as other methods
- **Young Ambassadors or Alumni programmes** - where young people share their personal experiences of mobility to help other young people understand the value and structure of these programs. Seeing peers succeed in Erasmus+ or ESC can help shift the perception that these are elite or inaccessible programmes and can inspire others to get involved.

Considering that **nearly all of the methods above are already in use** within the Erasmus+ 2021-2027 and ESC programmes, there is a need to improve, enhance or expand the existing approaches.

What else is good to know?

The Eurodesk Youth Info Survey 2025 shows that almost all young people are open to going abroad (98% of the respondents), and that almost all of them also see mobility as beneficial to their educational pathway, as well as to their personal and professional development (95% of respondents). The survey also showed that hybrid and virtual experiences are much less interesting for young people than in-person mobility. Young people are rather experienced in searching for mobility opportunities, and they mainly use web search, social media, friends and family as their information sources. Young people are also active social media users, especially in case of Instagram and YouTube, with young teenagers more likely to use TikTok, and young adults more likely to use Facebook.

Nevertheless, only about 40% of the respondents went abroad for a mobility period, often motivated by having fun and doing something meaningful at the same time. Those who did go abroad were extremely satisfied with their experiences: 69% said it was an amazing experience, and further 26% said it was a good one. 97% of those who went abroad were also willing to encourage others to go for their mobility experience. On the other hand, those who did not go abroad often state that they did not have enough information or did not even think about it, and lack of information and administrative problems are high on the list of general barriers to mobility (together with financial aspects). This showcases how important availability of information is for young people when it comes to their decisions to go abroad.

Do you want to read more?

Youth Info Survey 2025: Mobility and the Role of Youth Information. Online, available at <https://eurodesk.eu/eurodesk-youth-info-survey-2025/>

REPORT FROM THE COMMISSION (...) on the interim evaluation of the 2021-2027 Erasmus+ programme and the final evaluation of the 2014-2020 Erasmus+ programme. Online, available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/HTML/?uri=CELEX:52025DC0395&qid=1752646664581>

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